

EXAMINING THE INFLUENCE OF SUBSIDY REMOVAL, INSECURITY ON INFLATION IN NIGERIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

In recent years, Nigerians have been facing serious economic and security challenges, including the removal of fuel subsidies, rising insecurity which include the removal of fuel subsidies or subsidy, rising insecurity and high inflation rates. This research examined the influence of subsidy removal and insecurity on inflation in the Nigerian economy. The main objectives of the study were to examine the correlation between subsidy removal and inflation in the Nigerian economy and also investigate the correlation between insecurity and inflation in the Nigerian economy. The study adopted a descriptive design of survey type while the population of the study covers some selected citizens across Borno States respectively. A simple random sampling technique was used to obtain a sample of 200 respondents. Data were collected through a self-structured questionnaire and the collected data were analyzed using, percentages and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used to test the stated hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that the removal of fuel subsidies increased the inflation rate in the economy. Furthermore, it was discovered from the findings of the study that insecurity such as banditry, Boko-Haram insurgency, kidnapping, and the farmers-herdsmen crisis resulted in inflation in the Nigerian economy. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the revenue from subsidy removal should be channeled towards projects or programmes that will reduce its removal effects on the citizens by the government. Also, efficient and effective palliative programmes in terms of subsidized transportation systems, provision of subsidized foods and increases in minimum wages to employees. Furthermore, the government should also implement rights strategies that would effectively tackle and curb the issue of insecurity.

Keywords: Fuel Subsidy Removal, Insecurity, Inflation, Nigeria Economy

Introduction

Nigeria, Africa's largest economy has struggled with various development challenges. The total removal of fuel subsidies in 2023, coupled with escalating

insecurity and inflation, has exacerbated these challenges. This research delves into the effects of these factors on the economy, citizens, and the overall development of Nigeria. Because the protection of people

and property from domestic and international threats is essential for the operation of markets and the incentives to invest and innovate, Nigeria is a country endowed with an abundance of natural and human resources, but despite this, it still experiences economic instability brought on by several factors, including inflation and insecurity. (Amana, Aigbedion & Zubair, 2020). This justifies the essence many countries, developed and developing strive to maintain economic stability through ensuring peace and security across the nation. This is because any nation experiencing unrest situations in terms of insecurity would find it very difficult to thrive and enjoy economic growth.

Besides, ensuring justice, empowerment, employment, effective service delivery, and a high standard of living are all components of good government anticipated by all citizens. However, the removal of subsidies and other anti-national activities, along with rising levels of insecurity, pose a serious threat to human rights, national laws and regulations, and the economy in general (Mazumdar and Bhattacharjee 2019). People naturally and often experience infringement of human rights anywhere bad governance thrives. These issues affect trade balance, employment, price, output, poverty, inequality, defense spending, government budget patterns, sociopolitical environment, and a host of other factors (Abdulkarim & Saidatulakmal, 2022). Many have claimed that violent extremism and instability could, through several mechanisms, have a short-term detrimental effect on economic growth ((Isola et al. 2019).

In addition to the challenges of insecurity ravaging the nation's economy, comes the issue of fuel subsidy removal. Fuel costs will rise to market levels as a result of the withdrawal of government financial assistance for fuel (Peterson & Obiora, 2023). This raises the price of

gasoline and may have negative social and economic effects on the nation's residents in addition to raising the inflation rate (Nichola & Washima, 2024). The subsequent consequences of eliminating gasoline subsidies hurt people's level of life. People pay a premium for the goods and services they buy. The idea that the fossil fuel subsidy is a sort of help since it lowers the cost of gasoline for the underprivileged makes the elimination of the subsidy controversial. Despite this persuasive argument, a substantial body of research demonstrates the detrimental effects of fuel subsidies, which include rising air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions according to Peterson and Obiora (2023), traffic jams and early deaths (Parry, Black, and Vernon, 2021), lost tax revenue, and increased inequality between the rich and the poor, not to mention higher inflation rates (McCulloch, Moerenhout, and Yang, 2021).

Furthermore, the various economic challenges posed by insecurity and subsidy removal on the citizens of Nigeria as well as on the growth and development of the Nigerian economy cannot be overemphasized. The effects of fuel subsidies on the Nigerian economy have been the subject of numerous studies. For example, Umar and Umar (2013) and Siddig et al. (2014), as cited in Omotosho (2019), observed that the country's fuel subsidy regime distorts fiscal planning, encourages inefficient consumption, and increases inequality as wealthier households benefit more. Siddig et al. (2014) also demonstrated that the removal of fuel subsidies increases GDP and lowers household income. Other studies have shown that the removal of fuel subsidies in Nigeria could lead to inflation and lower economic welfare (Adenikinju, 2009); negatively impact economic growth and lower household income (Ocheni, 2015); and decrease the competitiveness of firms (Bazilian and Onyeji, 2012).

According to Nicholas & Washima (2024), the vast majority of Nigerians are unintentionally watching and feeling the bad effects of the elimination of gasoline subsidies. As a result, there have been job losses in the unorganized sector, as well as a drop in economic growth, an increase in inflation, poverty, crude theft, crime, and the price of petroleum products. As a result, the elimination of fuel subsidies has unavoidably increased living expenses nationwide and put pressure on the general populace; as a result, Nigerians are currently coping with the knock-on effects of the removal of fuel subsidies, transportation costs and the cost of necessities have increased dramatically nationwide (Karl, 1997).

Because of the high cost of transportation combined with other high costs of means of subsistence resulting from the removal of fuel subsidies, an abundance of commodities will bring less money to manufacturers rather than more, meaning that the high rate of inflation caused by the removal of fuel subsidies may spell economic disaster rather than prosperity among producers of goods and services. In this sense, poverty becomes inevitable. Long-term and short-term poverty will rise as a result of the country's inflation brought on by the elimination of gasoline subsidies. Families will experience both short-term and long-term suffering as well as hunger (Nicholas & Washima (2024). Individually, the elimination of fuel subsidies may result in lower disposable incomes, a decline in immunity for the majority of Nigerians, a shorter life expectancy, difficulty accessing medical care, high drug prices, and the inability to pay for basic education in many areas of the nation, particularly the north of Nigeria. More families could experience starvation, more malnourished youngsters might wail in agony, and more parents might weep over their hopeless kids.

The purchasing power of middle-class and lower-class customers will decline, and small enterprises will experience pressure on their profit margins due to increased expenses and lower sales volumes. And if they try to pass the cost down to the customer, the latter may decide not to buy at all or to buy less, which will result in a decline in customer support and a business collapse. Furthermore, in the event that social assistance programs or economic safety nets are lacking to lessen the financial hardship brought on by the elimination of gasoline subsidies, the withdrawal of subsidies may disproportionately affect vulnerable and impoverished populations (Nicholas & Washima, 2024). Besides, the possibility of an increase in criminality is another detrimental microeconomic effect of the withdrawal of gasoline subsidies (Shagali and Yusuf, 2022). Following the elimination of fuel subsidies, the price of gasoline increased, which might result in more crimes such fuel theft from refinery warehouses, private residences, automobiles, and electric generators owned by individuals. As more Nigerians struggle to make ends meet, the crime rate may rise.

The withdrawal of gasoline subsidies might have a negative macroeconomic impact, including a potential slowdown in the pace of economic growth, according to Peterson and Obiora (2023), who cite Houeland (2020). The elimination of gasoline subsidies would result in higher costs for necessities. As a result of growing costs, stagnating salaries, and a national minimum wage, people and small companies would have less discretionary cash. As a result, consumer spending will decline, which will reduce aggregate demand. A decrease in consumption would result in a lackluster demand from consumers for the products and services that businesses provide. As a result, the rate of economic growth may be

slowed and economic production and GDP may decline (Peterson & Obiora, 2023).

Over time, insecurity has been a significant obstacle to the nation's economic progress, and one of the detrimental effects of Fulani herders is the threat they pose to lives and property, which tends to impede efforts to forge new trade connections and spur agricultural growth. Nigeria's ongoing conflicts between farmers and herders are not a recent development, particularly in the country's north. What is relatively new, though, are the numerous news stories about farmers and herders fighting across the nation's states and regions—particularly the Southwest and South East (Chukwu, Utobo and Ufere, 2022).

To identify the various economic impacts of insecurity on the Nigerian economy, Bello, Agunyai & Amusan (2022), posited that acts of banditry have resulted in increased insecurity, which exacerbates the nation's death toll, population relocation, and property devastation (Bashir, 2017; Adeniyi, 2015; Abubakar, 2019). Nigeria ranked sixth (8.23) on the 2021 Global Terrorism Index as a result of the country's high banditry rate, indicating an escalating level of insecurity (Global Terrorism Index, 2021). Furthermore, in the words of Kosy (2013), any country facing security issues faces threats to its governance and economic progress. Nigeria's current state of insecurity is appalling; people are living in terror amid extreme poverty as a result of poor productivity and growing unemployment, companies are in dormant states, people are being uprooted, investments are being restricted, and lives are being wasted daily. The macroeconomic environment of Nigeria has been seriously threatened by bombings, particularly in the country's north, which have presented significant obstacles (Ajufu, 2013).

From the foregoing, Okereke (2012) and Bello (2013) as cited by Udeh, Eyikorogha, Ekoyo and Obiagu (2021), noted that farmers are afraid of herdsmen and bandits, who have left many families homeless, some children orphaned, and some who have managed to survive to seek asylum in their country of origin. As a result, farmers are unable to peacefully engage in their regular daily farming activities. Similar to this, attacks by bandits and the ongoing conflicts between Fulani herdsmen and farmers have frequently stoked religious animosity between Christians and Muslims. This is because a higher proportion of victims in the affected states—Benue, Taraba, and Nassarawa, to name a few—appeared to be Christians, while there are fewer attacks in other states where the majority population is Muslim (Obi, Chinweze & Onyejebu, 2018).

Comparably, recent research by Okereke (2012) and Kasarachi (2016) has clearly demonstrated that a major conflict between Fulani herdsmen and farmers has resulted in the loss of lives, priceless properties, and a significant area of arable agricultural farmlands destroyed, posing a serious threat to food security since farmers could no longer go to the fields and harvest their produce out of fear of being attacked (Obi, Chinweze, and Onyejebu, 2018). The recent killings and displacement reported by bandits and herdsmen on communities and farmlands have caused many farmers to lose their primary source of income and have created an intolerable situation in the community.

Remarkably, armed herdsmen who frequently let their cattle wander off to graze on the farmers' crops and agricultural products are frequently the catalyst for the killing of cows, which farmers allege is the main source of violence between herdsmen and farmers (Udeh, et al., 2021). The armed herdsmen and bandits responsible for the recent wave of attacks and killings in modern-day Nigeria have

been noted to have seriously threatened Nigeria's unity as a nation and to have disrupted political stability, socioeconomic, religious, and educational activities (Kasarachi, 2016). As the attack intensified, thousands of people were forced to flee their homes and their socioeconomic lives in order to protect themselves. As a result, it is undeniable that Nigeria is at a crossroads and is gradually becoming a society more prone to conflict (Okereke, 2012). As a result, many Nigerians began to experience severe psychological imbalance on a daily basis as the situation worsened.

The narratives of religion, land ownership rights, political power rotation, ethnicity, and indigenous settlers' arguments have all been hotly debated in the past in the northern section of Nigeria, where the Hausa-Fulani ethnic group dominates and competes with other minority groups. The largely Christian southern regions of Nigeria cannot be claimed to be like this. However, because of the friendly links between the sedentary farmers and herders, Fulani settlers and their families have been welcomed and allowed into host communities in Nigeria during the last several decades, particularly in the southern region of the nation (Genyi, 2014). The relationship between the two groups has gotten worse with the recent uptick in conflicts (Chigozie, 2012).

The current practices of open grazing and livestock rearing in Nigeria are not environmentally sustainable. Several gaps have made the crisis of conflicts and clashes surrounding open grazing in Nigeria worse. These gaps include a lack of a robust mechanism for stakeholder participation in land reform processes, inadequate information access, a lack of robust legal protection for pastoralists in the country's legal framework, and a lack of access to effective conflict resolution mechanisms in the event of a dispute (Ogboru and Adejonwo-Osho 2018).

Nigerians' ability to get food has been severely impacted by the recent attacks by Fulani herdsmen since agricultural yields have decreased. Because of this and their fear of being killed, farm owners have been forced to relocate or completely give up on farming with their crops. In a similar vein, reports indicate that Fulani herdsmen have killed and driven out several farmers in Nigeria, with the most recent attacks resulting in the deaths of at least forty people in one village. Summarily, from the foregoing, it can be deduced that subsidy removal and insecurity across the nation grossly affect the economy of Nigeria. This calls for an urgent intervention to enable the citizens of the country to live and conduct their economic activities with ease and productively (Chukwu, et al., 2022).

However, food production in the country has been hampered by the issues caused by insecurity. Due to banditry and herdsmen's actions, including kidnapping, destroying farmlands and crops, and even killing farmers on a regular basis, farmers now find it impossible to engage in agricultural operations. The residents are definitely affected overall by these operations, as seen by the high cost of living and food shortages.

Summarily, the influence of subsidy removal and insecurity on inflation in the Nigerian economy are:

1. Kidnapping and Banditry have fostered unrest situation leading to an increased inflation rate
2. Farmer-herdsmen clashes contribute to the shortage of human power available for agricultural and other economic practices
3. Food shortage across the nation influences the prices of goods and services
4. Insecurity hinders foreign investors from investing in Nigeria
5. Insecurity increases migration rates across the country

6. Fuel subsidy removal leads to increases in prices of factors of production
7. Fuel subsidy removal contributes to an increase in the prices of goods and services
8. There is an increase in transportation fares as a result of fuel subsidy removal
9. Low standard of living is experienced due to fuel subsidy removal
10. Fuel subsidy removal has resulted in low patronage of goods and services in Nigeria

Therefore, from the foregoing, it is evident that there exists a correlation between fuel subsidy removal, insecurity and inflation rates. In the presence of various insecurity challenges, citizens are confronted with some challenges related to economic meltdowns or recession. However, people tend to enjoy some economic benefits resulting from fuel subsidies because people do not need excessive labour or effort to enjoy an average standard of living as goods and services are at moderate prices. The removal of subsidies increases the prices of goods and services thereby reducing the purchasing power of the currency and leaving the people to strive to meet up with their daily needs. Hence, this study examined the influence of subsidy removal and insecurity on inflation in the Nigerian economy.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the interconnectedness of subsidy removal, insecurity and inflation in the Nigerian economy. Specifically, the study

1. investigated the influence of fuel subsidy removal on inflation in the Nigerian economy
2. determined influence of insecurity on inflation in the Nigerian economy

3. examined the correlation between subsidy removal and inflation in the Nigerian economy
4. determined the correlation between Insecurity and inflation in the Nigerian economy

Research Questions

1. What are the correlations between fuel subsidy removal and inflation in the Nigerian economy?
2. What is the correlation between insecurity and inflation in the Nigerian economy?

Research Hypotheses

- H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between fuel subsidy removal and inflation in Nigerian economy
- H₀₂: There is no significant correlation between insecurity and inflation in Nigerian economy

Methodology

The study employed quantitative and descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of selected individuals in across Borno and Kwara States respectively. Questionnaire being the instrument of data collection were given to 200 respondents. The instrument was subjected to face, content and construct validity and the test re-test method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. The retrieved data were subjected to statistical analysis using frequency distribution, mean and standard deviation and Pearson Product Monument Correlation Coefficient.

Result and Findings

Research Question one: What is the influence of fuel subsidy removal on inflation in Nigerian economy

Table 1: Responses on the Correlation between fuel subsidy removal and inflation rate in the Nigeria Economy

<i>N = 200</i>					
S/N	STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD
		4	3	2	1
1.	Fuel subsidy in some way reduces the cost of production of goods and services	75 (37.5%)	55 (27.5%)	40 (20.0%)	30 (15.0%)
2.	Fuel subsidy fuel removal leads to increases in factors of production	70 (35.0%)	65 (32.5%)	20 (10.0%)	45 (22.5%)
3.	Fuel subsidy removal contributes to an increase in the prices of goods and services	65 (32.5%)	55 (27.5%)	40 (20.0%)	40 (20.0%)
4.	There is increase in transportation fee as a result of fuel subsidy removal	100 (50.0%)	55 (27.5%)	35 (17.5%)	10 (5.0%)
5.	High cost of living is experienced due to fuel subsidy removal	85 (42.5%)	35 (17.5%)	-	80 (40.0%)
6.	Fuel subsidy removal has resulted in low patronage of goods and services in Nigeria	145 (72.5%)	40 (20.0%)	5 (2.5%)	10 (5.0%)

37.5% strongly agreed to the item “fuel subsidy in some way reduces the cost of production of goods and services”, 27,5% agreed, 20% disagreed and 15% strongly disagreed.

Also, 35.0% strongly agreed with the item “fuel subsidy removal leads to increases in factors of production, 32.5% agreed, 10.0% disagreed and 22.5% of the total respondents strongly disagreed.

Furthermore, it was discovered that 32.5% strongly agreed with the item “fuel subsidy removal contributes to increasing in the prices of goods and services”, 27.5% agreed, 20.0% disagreed and 20.0% strongly disagreed.

Similarly, 50.0% of the total respondents strongly agreed with the item “There is an increase in transportation fare as a result of fuel subsidy removal, 27.5% agreed, 17.5% disagreed and 5.0% strongly disagreed.

Additionally, it was observed that 42.5% strongly agreed with the item “High cost of living is experienced due to fuel subsidy removal, 17.5% agreed, while 40.0% strongly disagreed.

Finally, 72.5% strongly agreed with the item “Fuel subsidy removal has resulted in low patronage of goods and services in Nigeria, 20.0% agreed, 2.5% disagreed and 5.0% strongly disagreed.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of Insecurity on inflation in the Nigerian economy?

Table 2: Respondents Responses on the influence of insecurity on inflation in Nigerian Economy

		N= 200			
S/N.	STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD
		4	3	2	1
1	Insecurity is a common occurrence in Nigeria	60 (30.0%)	70 (35.0%)	30 (15.0%)	40 (20.0%)
2.	Kidnapping and Banditry has fosters unrest situation leading to increased inflation rate	80 (40.0%)	50 (25.0%)	55 (27.5%)	15 (7.5%)
3.	Farmer-herdsmen clashes contribute to the shortage of human power available for agricultural and other economic practices	120 (60.0%)	30 (15.0%)	32 (16.0%)	18 (9.0%)
4.	Food shortage across the nation influences the prices of goods and services	138 (69.0%)	22 (21.0%)	30 (15.0%)	30 (15.0%)
5.	Insecurity hinders foreign investors from investing in Nigeria	165 (82.5%)	10 (5.0%)	15 (7.5%)	10 (5.0%)
6.	Insecurity increases migration rates across the country	120 (60.0%)	80 (40.0%)	-	-

30.0% strongly agreed with the item “Insecurity is a common occurrence in Nigeria”, 35% agreed, 15.0% disagreed and 20.0% strongly disagreed.

Also, 40.0% strongly agreed with the item “kidnapping and banditry have fostered unrest situation leading to the increased inflation rate, 25% agreed, 27.5% disagreed and 7.5% strongly disagreed.

Furthermore, 60.0% strongly agreed with the item “farmer-herdsmen conflicts contribute to the shortage of human power available for agricultural and other economic practices, 15.0% agreed, 16.0% disagreed, and 9.0% strongly disagreed.

Similarly, 69.0% strongly agreed to the item “food shortage across the nation influences the prices of goods and services, 21.0% agreed, 15.0% disagreed while 15.0% strongly disagreed.

Additionally, 82.5% strongly agreed with the item “Insecurity hinders foreign investors from investing in Nigeria”, 5.0% agreed, 7.5% disagreed and 5.0% strongly disagreed.

Finally, 60.0% strongly agreed with the item “Insecurity increases migration rates across the country”, 40.0% agreed, while none disagreed or strongly disagreed.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

There is no significant correlation between subsidy removal and inflation rates in Nigeria's economy

Table 3: PMCC analysis on the connection between subsidy removal and inflation.

	Variables	R	Df	Sig. Level
Subsidy Removal	X (441.8)	0.927335	30.0	0.05
Inflation	Y (255.56)			

The analysis above revealed that $r = 0.927$ at a 0.05 level of significance and 30.0 degrees of freedom. This indicates a strong positive correlation between the variables. From the analysis, the null

hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant correlation between subsidy removal and inflation rates in the Nigerian economy.

Hypothesis Two

There is a significant correlation between Insecurity and inflation rates in the Nigeria economy

Table 4: PMCC analysis on the connection between Insecurity and Inflation rate in the Nigeria Economy

	Variables	r	Df	Sig. Level
Insecurity	X (413.5)	0.89233	38	0.05
Inflation Rate	Y (255.56)			

The analysis above revealed that $r = 0.89233$ at 0.05 level of significance and 38 degrees of freedom. This indicates a strong positive correlation between the variables. From the analysis, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant correlation between subsidy removal and inflation rates in the Nigeria economy

nationwide and put pressure on the general populace; as a result, Nigerians are currently coping with the knock-on effects of the removal of fuel subsidies, transportation costs and the cost of necessities have increased dramatically nationwide. Additionally, the study of Shagali & Yusuf (2022) also posited that the possibility of an increase in criminality is one of the major effects of the withdrawal of fuel subsidies, thus the elimination of fuel subsidies might result to more crimes involvement by the populace of the nation such as fuel theft from refinery warehouses, private residences, automobiles, and electric generators owned by individuals. As more Nigerians struggle to make ends meet, the crime rate may rise.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that there is a correlation between subsidy removal and inflation in Nigerian economy, this is supported by the findings of Nicholas & Washima (2024), where they stated that due to the removal of fuel subsidies, there have been job losses in the unorganized sector, as well as a drop in economic growth, an increase in inflation, poverty, crude theft, crime, and the price of petroleum products. As a result, the elimination of fuel subsidies has unavoidably increased living expenses

In addition, the finding of the study indicated that there is a correlation between insecurity and inflation in Nigerian economy. This is justified by Awotokun, Nwozor and Olanrewaju (2020), who identified herders-farmers conflicts as a serious threat to the growth and

development of the Nigerian economy in terms of loss of resources and human lives. It also found that these conflicts have jeopardized the prospects of meeting the global goals of poverty eradication and zero hunger. The study equally found that the government has no specific set of strategies to contain the conflicts and that its equivocation and unwillingness to prosecute the architects and perpetrators of the conflicts has emboldened them.

Furthermore, the study of Ajibefun (2018), revealed that insecurity as a result of conflicts between farmers and herdsmen led to destruction of crops. The social effect of the menace of Fulani herdsmen are loss of human life, sexual harassment of human life, acquiring of weapons/arms, reduction in quality of social relationship, reduction of social support and high cases of rape while the economic effect of the menace of Fulani herdsmen are reduction in output and income of farmers/nomads, loss of produce in storage, displacement of farmers, scarcity of agricultural products, loss of house and properties and infrastructural damages. Additionally, according to Kasarachi (2016), the armed herdsmen and bandits responsible for the recent wave of attacks and killings in modern-day Nigeria have been noted to have seriously threatened Nigeria's unity as a nation and to have disrupted political stability, socioeconomic, religious, and educational activities. All this sum together results to decrease in economic practices that would foster Nigerian economic growth and development.

Recommendations

The study recommends that the revenue from subsidy removal should be channeled towards projects/programmes that will reduce its removal effects on the citizens by the government. Also, efficient and effective palliative programmes in terms of the subsidized transportation system, provision of subsidized food items, and

increase in minimum wages to employees. Also, implementing policies to reduce inflation (e.g., monetary policy, price controls) as well as investing in security measures to address insecurity challenges, and lastly, promoting economic diversification and development to reduce dependence on fuel subsidies and mitigate the effects of insecurity and inflation. By understanding the interconnectedness of these factors, policymakers can develop targeted solutions to address the root causes of economic challenges in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study was conducted to evaluate the interconnectedness of fuel subsidy removal, insecurity and inflation in Nigerian economy. It was discovered that there is a correlation between subsidy removal and inflation rates in the Nigerian economy. This is because it was believed that the availability of fuel subsidy reduces the cost of production of goods of goods and services thereby leading to increase in production rates. However, its removal fosters high costs of factors of production, increases the prices of goods and services, increases transportation fee, high costs of living as well as low patronage of goods and services.

In addition, the study revealed that there is a relationship between insecurity and inflation rates. Insecurity such as terrorism, banditry, herdsmen crisis, kidnapping amongst others were found to have a recue effects on the inflation rate. This was attributed to unrest situation, shortage of human power available for agricultural and other economic practices, shortage in food supply, lack of sufficient foreign investors and increase in migration rates.

The study concluded that there is a strong correlation between fuel subsidy removal, insecurity and increased inflation in the Nigerian economy. Besides, no economy can grow in the presence of

insecurity, fuel subsidy removal and high inflation rate. This is because the effects of these elements are felt by the citizens of the nation thereby reducing their contributions to the growth of the economy.

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